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Abstract. We know that a preschooler is the age when he can use the basic skills of literacy in his daily activities. Therefore, in order to teach the child literacy skills, to attract him, it is necessary to consciously conduct literacy activities every day. Because the more a child meets letters and written words, the stronger his language skills will be. This article talks about different ways to help preschoolers develop their literacy skills.

Keywords: literacy, language, alphabet, word, letter, segmentation, phonics, interactive, communication, reading, ability, technology, integration.

At preschool age, the circle of communication between children in contact with children is expanding, which requires a child with a full-fledged means of communication, the main of which is speech. High requirements for the development of areas of speech and the development of more complex activities of the child. The development of speech is going in several directions: its practical use in communicating with other people is improving, they are, at the same time, a means of thinking, a means of thinking, a basis for the reconstruction of a means of thinking. Studying at school is one of the main components of children's readiness to develop speech. The development of speech is considered to be the development of the skills of understanding and using the language: the development of futhemektitikudic hearing and sound analysis, vocabulary, the composition of words, the formation of grammatical categories, communicative skills, the development of skills and skills of connected speech . Language acquisition is an important condition for mental development, because the content of the historical experience established by the child during ontogenesis is summarized and expressed in the form of speech, and primarily in words. The technique uses methods developed in didactics. The method of speech development is defined as a method of activity of the teacher and children that ensures the formation of speech skills and abilities. Distinguish three method groups - visual, verbal and practical. This division is quite conditional, since there is no sharp boundary between them. Visual methods are accompanied by words, and verbal descriptive methods are used. Practical methods involve both words and visuals. Some methods are computational and visual, others verbal or practical, depending on the spread of techniques for visualization, words or actions as the source and basis of

speech. Kindergarten used visual methods more often. Apply as direct and indirect methods. The direct method applies to observation and its types: excursions, inspection of rooms, observation of natural objects. These methods are aimed at collecting speech content and provide communication between two signaling systems. Indirect methods are surprisingly accurate based on the use of calculus. These are toys, pictures, photos, descriptions of pictures and storytelling through toys, toys and pictures. They are used to strengthen knowledge, develop vocabulary, the generalizing function of words, and teach coherent speech. Mediated by me todes can also be used to identify objects and events that cannot be identified directly.

Making literacy a part of everyday life is very rewarding. It is also necessary to use hands-on experiences that allow children to experience safely and explore their world. Each child learns and develops language skills at a different time, but all young children need: * Opportunities to develop and practice developing skills; * Praise for motivation and action; * Understanding that continuous learning is a family value; * Help parents and other caregivers plan developmentally appropriate learning activities; * A special place for study and practical training. In order to prepare a child for a successful education at school, it is necessary to create appropriate conditions for him to acquire all the riches of his native language. The development of a child's speech depends to a large extent on his psyche, healthy, vigorous growth, moral qualities, ensuring the proper implementation of the curriculum, and the quality of the manuals. It is necessary to find a solution to these issues in preschool education and to focus on education to be able to speak fluently in one's mother tongue. In the training sessions on the development of oral speech, the main focus is on the development of children's oral speech, the correct formation of speech from the grammatical point of view, and the continuation of the formation of morphological and syntactic aspects of speech: simple and complex. to make joint sentences, to teach children to use all word groups, to improve the skills of correct use of number to noun, adjective to noun, adjective to verb when speaking, to pronounce sounds and words correctly, emphasis is placed on speaking fluently and telling independent stories. Teaching independent storytelling plays an important role in the development of oral speech. Children are taught to compose stories based on the topics suggested by the teacher, looking at the events and pictures in their lives. The stories of the children of the preparatory group should be connected in content, have a certain consistency, and be grammatically correct. In our independent Republic of Uzbekistan, special attention is paid to the literacy of everyone. It is known that the main task of reading classes in the process of

literacy training is to introduce students to sounds and letters, to teach children the correct pronunciation of ulair, to develop correct, conscious, expressive reading skills in children. consists of formation. Also, this period has a special place due to its responsibility in enriching students' vocabulary, developing their connected speech, enriching their knowledge, forming their thinking, listening, and receiving intuition. To teach reading, first of all, the student should be well introduced to sounds and letters. When introducing sounds and letters, the principle of separating sounds from syllables is observed. Introduction to the letter can be done in several different ways:

1. A story related to the meaningful picture is created using the question-and-answer method. From it, the necessary sentence and then the necessary word are extracted, and then analysis work is organized on the word as above.
2. Based on the word, the sound that is studied with the help of analytical exercises is isolated. For example: moon. The teacher shows a picture of the moon, students say its name - a word. The teacher says the sound o by stretching it (o-o-o-y) and asks the students which sound they are stretching. After the students pronounce the o sound, a question-and-answer session is held about its characteristics. Words with the sound o are invented. After that, the letter o is displayed from a cursive letter or from the pictorial alphabet. Special attention is paid to remembering the shape of the letter o. Language and speaking skills. Strong language skills help preschoolers acquire other literacy skills more easily. This gives children a sense of confidence in acquiring knowledge and creative development. The more young children are exposed to letters and written words, the stronger and more durable their language skills will be. It is necessary to make learning and practicing alphabets an interesting activity. Do not limit the child to books and pencils. Use alphabet cookies or magnetic alphabets to help him understand the alphabet. Using every opportunity to help strengthen vocabulary is effective. Simple word games, even I'm a Spy, require the use of boring cars. Here, the child will have to show the object that starts with the given alphabet. Reading and writing skills. Writing is a skill that takes practice. So take some time each day to help your child improve their writing skills. Create some fun writing activities. You can make a shopping list with your child and ask him to write down the easier ones. So if your child wants a toy, ask them to add it to your list. It helps them feel important and enjoy their training. It is clear to everyone that the act of reading and writing in a purposeful manner during teaching children to read and write is considered a reading and writing skill. And this skill requires knowledge, because any skill cannot be formed without knowledge. At this point, it is worth saying that it is necessary to

consciously set aside time every day to engage your child in activities that will help him improve his literacy skills. Because as a parent, you are your child's first teacher!

A speech model is a correct, premeditated speech activity and their direction intended for imitation by the teacher. The sample should be usable in content and form. Pronounced clearly, loudly and slowly. At this level, a model for imitation is given, which is presented before the beginning of children's speech activity. But sometimes, especially in older age groups, an example can be used after children's speech, but at the same time it serves not for imitation, but for comparison and correction. The pattern is used to solve all problems. It is especially important in small groups. Repeating is the same element of speech (sound, word, phrase) that is deliberately repeated repeatedly with the aim of memorizing it. In practice, various options are used for repetition: for the teacher, for other children, repetition together, teacher and children, chorus. It is important to offer children repetition in the context of an interesting activity for them. Explanation Revealing the nature of specific events or methods of action. In broad didactics, games are used to reveal the meanings of words, to explain rules and actions, as well as in the process of observing and examining objects. Directions - explaining to children how to act to achieve a certain result. Separate instructions for teaching, organization and discipline. Assessment of children's speech - reasonable judgments about the child's speech that describe the quality of speech activity. Assessment should be not only descriptive, but also educational in nature. It is given so that all children can do it. The impact of assessment on highly emotional children. To achieve this, it is necessary to take into account individual and age characteristics: in this way, it increases the child's speech activity, interest in speech activity, regulates his behavior. For this assessment, first of all, negative qualities of speech are emphasized, speech defects are corrected with the help of samples and other methodical methods.

In conclusion, it can be said that as a solid foundation of the education system and in the pre-school education system, which is considered as the first model, it is necessary to deepen and enrich the first knowledge reserves of the young generation, who are the owners of the future generation. After all, if their foundation of knowledge is solid, in the future, when they start studying in the school education system, when they reach the period of literacy, they will easily enrich their stock of knowledge on the basis of this foundation.

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